

THE AURA OF THE DIGITALLY FABRICATED

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INTRODUCTION

This workshop explores the meaning embedded in our everyday products, and how the digital manufacturing with CNC machining and 3D printing are changing the possibilities in embedding personalized content in the artefacts. Combined with the traditional handicrafts, but augmented with the digitally controlled, the resulting products can reflect the meaning of all parties, the designer, the process of making, and the end-user.

VISION

The workshop deals with the question of how we assign meaning to the things we live with. Traditionally, the hand-made aura is a valuable meaning-making factor, just as the precision quality of the mass-manufactured object. With the possibility of having the precision of a machine-made product, and the uniqueness of an atelier service, digitally fabricated artefacts balance between the different aspects of the meaning, of the aura of the artefacts. This kind of meaning making needs new kinds of production networks; new product-service-systems, that leverage internet, machines and traditional crafts.

BACKGROUND:

Two case studies are used to inspire discussion and projection in the local cultural context, to find out in which kinds of products the promise of the digital fabrication can best be utilized.

1. Locatable

Locatable is a dining table which has a carved street network filled with resin on it. It is meant to be ordered online with a simple interface, where one only has to specify a single address. The address defines the cutout area from the OpenStreetMap database, which gets sent to a 3D milling studio. The tool bit has been previously defined for optimal aesthetic, and the vacuum table under the milling machine makes it extremely easy and fast to carve the street network on a wooden board. Once ready, the board is transported to another wood working studio close-by, where the grooves are filled with epoxy resin and subsequently sanded for the final aesthetic, before sent to the client. A map as a motif is both useful and aesthetically appealing, a location is often emotionally charged, and both present an optimal content for a personalized product.

2. Ciphering

<http://ciphering.me>

Ciphering is a piece of jewellery, whose form directly represents the message encoded in it. A simple web interface lets the client configure a date and two initials as well as the diameter of the ring. Based on these variables, software algorithm generates the 3D form. When the slits on its surface are aligned, it reveals the hidden digits that define its form, either casting a shadow, or seen as a silhouette on its surface.

The manufacturing process combines the old and the new: First, the forms are created with a lost-wax casting process using a high-resolution 3D wax printer. The 3D printed wax model is put in a container and liquid plaster is poured around it to

locatable.beta

Step 1:

Show Place

Step 2:

please enter your e-mail address and details so we can send you a price offer.

Send me a quote

Credits

Hybrid-Plattform.org UdK Berlin TU Berlin Bettin Bartmann Masonryte Recolloir

FALTAN CRÉDITOS
DE IMÁGENES

create a mold. After the plaster sets, the wax is melted out in a furnace, and molten silver or bronze is poured into the plaster mold. The plaster is then pulled away to reveal the noble metal, and the finished product is polished for a smooth surface.

The designer is responsible for the general form but the "meaning" is cast by the client.

EXPECTED AUDIENCE:

The workshop participants are expected to discuss the implications of digital manufacturing in the local context of handicrafts and design. After the introduction to the theme, small groups are assembled and ideas are sketched for potential explorations for product concepts, which resources they will employ, and how the information flow will be choreographed.

The results are assembled together to portray the range of possibilities to leverage digital manufacturing techniques to create a new kind of aura for customized products.

The workshop can host up to 14 participants. The relevant disciplines for the attendees range from product design, graphic design, and architecture to digital media, web development and design engineering.

SPACE NEEDED FOR THE WORKSHOP:

A room with a projector, or a big screen for the presentation. Tables to sketch out ideas on paper in small groups (a studio setup is preferred over a lecture-hall type spatial arrangement), and, if possible (but not mandatory), a short visit to a workshop with a milling machine or a 3D printer.

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